

Effect Of Intradialytic Exercise On Blood Pressure, Clearance, Biochemical Parameters And Health Related Quality Of Life Among Chronic Kidney Disease Patients Subjected To Hemodialysis : Analytical Comparative Study

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Abstract

Background: Chronic renal failure patients on maintenance hemodialysis often experience reduced dialysis adequacy, poor biochemical control, and diminished quality of life related to health (HRQoL). Intradialytic exercise has emerged as a potential adjunct to improve these outcomes.

Objective: To evaluate the effect of structured lower limb intradialytic exercise on dialysis adequacy, hemodynamic stability, biochemical markers, nutritional status, and HRQoL among patients with end-stage renal disease undergoing hemodialysis.

Methods: This analytical comparative study followed a crossover design and was conducted at NIMS Hospital, Jaipur. 19 eligible patients were divided into two groups (Group 1: n=10; Group 2: n=9) and subjected to alternating phases of exercise and control. Exercise involved 30 minutes of pedaling using a WERFiT device during the first two hours of hemodialysis sessions. Kt/V, blood pressure, serum urea, creatinine, electrolytes, nutritional indicators, and SF-12 HRQoL scores were monitored.

Results: Dialysis adequacy (Kt/V) significantly improved during the exercise phase. Hemodynamic parameters remained stable, with no adverse cardiovascular changes. Although biochemical parameters did not change significantly, favorable trends were observed in hemoglobin, urea, phosphorus, and potassium during the exercise phases. HRQoL showed significant improvement in both physical and mental component scores. Nutritional indicators like BMI, serum albumin, and total protein improved non-significantly. Complications such as hypotension and cramps were reduced during exercise phases.

Conclusion: Intradialytic lower limb exercise is a safe and feasible strategy that improves dialysis adequacy, enhances HRQoL, and may contribute positively to biochemical and nutritional stability. Its incorporation into routine hemodialysis care is strongly supported by these findings.

Keywords: Intradialytic exercise, Kt/V, hemodialysis, dialysis adequacy, biochemical parameters, SF-12, quality of life related to health, chronic kidney disease, PCS, MCS

Introduction:

Chronic Renal Failure (CRF) is a significant global health concern, especially in developing countries, placing a heavy financial burden on healthcare systems [1]. The estimated global prevalence of CRF is approximately 13.4%, with projections suggesting that between 4.9 to 7.1 million individuals with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) will require renal replacement therapy (RRT) [1]. Presently, over 2.5 million individuals are undergoing RRT, and this number is expected to double to 5.4 million by 2030 [2]. Diabetes and hypertension are the primary causes of CRF and their increasing incidence has contributed significantly to the global rise in CRF cases [3]. Although kidney transplantation is the preferred mode of RRT, hemodialysis (HD) remains the most common due to limited transplant availability [4]. While HD prolongs survival, it also contributes to physical and psychological challenges including diminished functional capacity, social isolation, and low self-esteem [5]. Patients frequently suffer from fatigue, weakness, elevated blood pressure, and uremic symptoms which contribute to poor quality of life related to health (HRQoL) [6]. The chronicity of HD results in muscle degradation, loss of body mass, and impaired mobility, which are exacerbated by hormonal changes, inflammation, inactivity, and metabolic complications [6]. Muscular atrophy affects a significant proportion (18–80%) of dialysis patients and is a major factor contributing to physical inactivity and limited functional performance [7]. Physical inactivity in HD patients is linked with poor clinical outcomes and increased mortality risk [9]. The National Kidney Foundation Disease Outcomes Quality Initiative (KDOQI) recommends exercise as a key component of rehabilitation in HD patients due to its cost-effectiveness and ability to alleviate uremic symptoms, regulate blood pressure, and improve overall quality of life [17]. Adequacy of dialysis is critical, as suboptimal dialysis is a major contributor to morbidity and mortality among patients; improving dialysis adequacy is essential for better patient outcomes [11]. Intradialytic exercise has emerged as a promising strategy to address these complications. Conducted during dialysis sessions, it improves muscle perfusion, facilitates urea mobilization, and enhances dialysis adequacy [10]. Exercise also promotes ion redistribution, helping to relieve pain and improve patient comfort [8]. Evidence indicates that sixty minutes of intradialytic exercise can achieve dialysis adequacy improvements comparable to increasing dialysis duration by twenty minutes [12]. Dialysis adequacy, a critical indicator of HD effectiveness, is commonly assessed using Kt/V and urea reduction ratio (URR). Adequate dialysis is defined as $Kt/V \geq 1.2$ and $URR \geq 65\%$ [13]. Among various methods, Online Clearance Monitoring (OCM) provides a noninvasive and practical way to assess Kt/V during HD sessions [14]. Additionally, intradialytic exercise is known to regulate blood pressure and significantly improve HRQoL [15]. Given these benefits, the present analytical comparative study was designed to evaluate the effect of intradialytic exercise on blood pressure, dialysis adequacy, biochemical parameters, and HRQoL among patients with CRF undergoing HD.

Material and Method:

This hospital-based analytical comparative study was conducted in the Hemodialysis Unit of the Department of Nephrology at NIMS Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan, to assess the effects of lower limb intradialytic exercise on dialysis adequacy, physiological stability, biochemical markers, nutritional status, and health-related quality of life in patients with chronic kidney disease. All patients undergoing maintenance hemodialysis were systematically screened using predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Eligible participants provided written informed consent. On the first day of the study, patients were assigned a number based on their order of arrival at the hemodialysis unit. Those with odd numbers were allocated to Group 1, while even-numbered patients were assigned to Group 2. This allocation formed the basis for a crossover study design, allowing each group to function as both study and control arms during different phases. The study was carried out over six months and divided into three distinct phases: Phase 1 (Months 1–2), where Group 1 underwent intradialytic exercise and Group 2 served as control; Phase 2 (Months 3–4), where Group 2 performed exercise while Group 1 served as control; and Phase 3 (Months 5–6), dedicated to data analysis. This design helped reduce inter-patient variability and strengthened the internal validity of findings.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Aged 18 to 60 years.
- ESRD patients on regular hemodialysis.
- Receiving hemodialysis at least two times/week, for three or four hrs/session.
- Minimum dialysis vintage of 3 months.
- Systolic BP <180 mmHg and diastolic <120 mmHg.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Recent hospitalization within last 3 months.
- Cardiovascular diseases.
- Acute myocardial ischemia, angina, or arrhythmia requiring treatment in past 3 months.
- Musculoskeletal disorders, fractured or paralyzed limbs.
- Lower limb vascular access or amputation.

The study enrolled 20 patients through convenience sampling; one participant from Group 2 was excluded due to other medical illness, resulting in a final sample of 19 (Group 1: n1=10, Group 2: n2=9). Baseline data included age, gender, dry weight, dialysis vintage, cause of kidney disease, and vascular access type. Patients were evaluated using the SF-12 questionnaire to establish initial quality of life related to health (HRQoL) scores. Physiological parameters including pre-, mid-, and post-dialysis blood pressure were systematically monitored. Dialysis details such as blood flow rate (BFR), dialysate flow rate (DFR), treatment duration, and Kt/V (assessed via Online Clearance Monitoring) were consistently recorded. Intradialytic complications were documented for safety evaluation. The exercise protocol was implemented using a WErFIT pedal exerciser during the first two hours of dialysis, structured into three 10-minute bouts with rest periods, targeting 900 to 1800 pedal cycles per session at 30 to 60 RPM. Nutritional status was evaluated monthly using dry weight, BMI, serum albumin, and total protein, while biochemical markers including hemoglobin, serum urea, creatinine, calcium, phosphorus, potassium, and sodium were measured. HRQoL was assessed monthly using the SF-12. Data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics mean and standard deviation were used for continuous variables. Independent sample t-tests were applied for between- and within-group comparisons. Chi-square tests analyzed categorical variables. Repeated measures ANOVA assessed longitudinal changes across study phases.

Observation and Result:

All participants underwent hemodialysis under standardized conditions, including a blood flow rate of 300 mL/min and a dialysate flow rate of 500 mL/min. Each dialysis session lasted for 4 hours, and all patients received dialysis twice per week. The Fresenius Medical Care F6HPS dialyzer, with a surface area of 1.3 m², was used for all patients to ensure consistency in dialysis delivery. Baseline demographic and medical history of the study participants were documented prior to the implementation of the intradialytic exercise. These variables included age, gender, height, dry weight, dialysis vintage, type of vascular access, cause of kidney disease, and addiction history. The most common cause of kidney disease in both groups was hypertension, followed by other conditions such as congenital kidney disease, glomerulonephritis with hypertension, nephrotic syndrome, nephrolithiasis, and polycystic kidney disease. Addiction history was minimal across both groups, with isolated cases of tobacco use, smoking, and a combination of smoking and alcohol use. A comparative analysis was carried out to assess baseline homogeneity between the groups [Table-1]. The comparison of Kt/V and physiological parameters between Group 1 and Group 2 showed a significant improvement in dialysis adequacy during the exercise phase, with a between-group p-value (P2 0.0075). However, within-group changes were not statistically significant (P1 > 0.05). All physiological parameters including pre-, mid-, and post-dialysis systolic and diastolic blood pressure remained stable with no significant changes within or between groups (P1 and P2 > 0.05). These findings suggest that intradialytic exercise improves dialysis clearance without compromising hemodynamic stability [Table-2]. Biochemical parameter comparisons showed no statistically significant changes within or between Group 1 and Group 2 during exercise and control phases (P1 and P2 > 0.05). Hemoglobin levels increased slightly in Group 2 during the exercise phase, and minor reductions in serum urea, phosphorus, and potassium levels were noted during exercise in both groups, indicating a positive trend. However, serum creatinine, calcium, and sodium remained stable. These findings suggest that intradialytic exercise may support biochemical balance without causing significant fluctuations in key metabolic markers [Table-3]. In this study, significant improvements were noted in both PCS and MCS scores during the exercise phases of Group 1 and Group 2 (P1 < 0.0001 and 0.0063 respectively), showing improved physical and mental well-being through exercise during dialysis. Between-group comparisons also showed significance in PCS (P2 = 0.0433) and MCS (P2 = 0.03125 and 0.00535), favoring the exercising group. While BMI, serum albumin, and total serum protein levels showed positive trends during the exercise phases in both groups, these changes were not statistically significant (P1 and P2 > 0.05). Overall, exercise demonstrated notable benefits for HRQoL and nutritional markers.[Table-4]

TABLE.1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Demographic and Medical History Variables in Group 1 and Group 2						
Demographics and Medical History	Group 1 (n1=10)		Group 2 (n2=09)		χ^2 value	P value
	No	In %	No	In %		
Age (In yr)						
≤ 25	1	10%	2	22.22%	3.32	0.344 (NS)
26 - 35	6	60%	2	22.22%		
36 - 45	3	30%	3	33.33%		
> 45	0	0%	2	22.22%		
Gender						
Male	7	70%	7	77.78%	0	1.000 (NS)
Female	3	30%	2	22.22%		
Height (In cm)						
150	1	10%	0	0.00%	5.02	0.414 (NS)
151-155	1	10%	3	33.33%		
156-160	0	0%	2	22.22%		
161-165	3	30%	2	22.22%		
166-170	3	30%	0	0.00%		
171-175	2	20%	2	22.22%		
Dry weight (In kg)						
35	0	0%	1	11.11%	1.57	0.814 (NS)
36-45	5	50%	3	33.33%		
46-55	3	30%	2	22.22%		
56-65	2	20%	2	22.22%		
≥66	0	0%	1	11.11%		
HD Vintage (In yr)						
0 - 2	5	50%	4	44.44%	0.81	0.848 (NS)
3 - 4	3	30%	3	33.33%		
4 - 5	1	10%	2	22.22%		
> 6	1	10%	0	0.00%		
Type of Vascular Access						
Left AVF	9	90%	8	88.89%	0	1.000 (NS)
Right AVF	1	10%	1	11.11%		
Cause for kidney Disease						
Hypertension	6	60%	5	55.56%	1.8	0.877 (NS)
Congenital kidney disease	2	20%	1	11.11%		
Nephrolithiasis	1	10%	0	0.00%		
Glomerulonephritis & HTN	1	10%	1	11.11%		
Polycystic kidney disease	0	0%	1	11.11%		
Nephrotic syndrome	0	0%	1	11.11%		
Addiction History						
Tobacco	1	10%	0	0.00%	1.39	0.709 (NS)
Alcohol	0	0%	0	0.00%		
Smoking	1	10%	0	0.00%		
Smoking & Alcohol Both	0	0%	1	11.11%		
[n1=number of patient in group1 n2= number of patient in group2 X2: Pearson X2 test P < 0.05 (significant) NS=Not significant HTN=Hypertension]						

TABLE.2 Kt/V & Physiological parameter within & Between group comparison of both group during Exercise and Control Phase				
Parameter	Group (n1=10) (n2=9)	Phases		P1 value
Kt/v	G1	EP	CP	0.1885
		2.28 ± 0.315	1.98 ± 0.285	
	G2	CP	EP	0.2557
		1.745 ± 0.22	2.08 ± 0.255	
	P2	0.0075*	0.8031	
	Pre HD SBP	G1	EP	CP
155.05±15.85			158.7±13.875	
G2		CP	EP	0.1187
		151.7±16.25	152.4±11.95	
P2		0.6552	0.30625	
Post HD DBP		G1	EP	CP
	88.655±5.455		90.315±4.765	
	G2	CP	EP	0.6066
		87.44±7.585	89.05±4.28	
	P2	0.701	0.57405	
	Mid HD SBP	G1	EP	CP
143.55±10.09			133.75±14.625	
G2		CP	EP	0.4268
		128.85±19.9	141.7±14.94	
P2		0.2071	0.2635	
Mid HD DBP		G1	EP	CP
	143.55±10.09		81.19±5.835	
	G2	CP	EP	0.1438
		79.35±9.965	84.85±6.625	
	P2	0.5573	0.2208	
	Post HD SBP	G1	EP	CP
146.25±13.9			139±13.4	
G2		CP	EP	0.441
		142.7±13.2	142.9±11.1	
P2		0.62295	0.5204	
Post HD DBP		G1	EP	CP
	85.475±6.05		83.625±5.1	
	G2	CP	EP	0.6192
		83.9±8.2	83.5±4.895	
	P2	0.6343	0.5204	

n1=number of patient in group1 n2= number of patient in group2 G1=Group1 G2=Group2 P1=value for comparing within group P2=value for comparing between group P=independent sample t-test
EP=Exercise Phase CP=Control Phase *P<0.05 (significant) SBP=Systolic Blood Pressure
DBP=Diastolic Blood Pressure HD=Hemodialysis

Graph-1 Mean Kt/v Comparison Group-1

Graph-2 Mean Kt/v Comparison Group-2

TABLE.3 Biochemical parameter within & Between group comparison of both group during Exercise and Control Phase				
Parameter	Group	Phases		P1- value
Hemoglobin	G1	EP	CP	0.9892
		8.495±2.485	8.325±2.29	
	G2	CP	EP	0.658
		7.285±0.76	8.33±0.92	
	P2	0.1862	0.8232	
	Pre HD S.Urea	G1	EP	CP
137.8±26.4			135.05±27.435	
G2		CP	EP	0.4967
		159.85±38.25	146.4±37.85	
P2		0.27635	0.5461	
Post HD s.Urea		G1	EP	CP
	38±15.02		51.2±19.785	
	G2	CP	EP	0.1592
		53.06±28.35	46.05±18.285	
	P2	0.205	0.5538	
	Pre HD S.creat	G1	EP	CP
10.515±2.475			11.575±2.845	
G2		CP	EP	0.4268
		10.605±2.015	10.9±2.09	
P2		0.79255	0.6403	
Post HD S.creat		G1	EP	CP
	3.205±1.09		4.225±1.39	
	G2	CP	EP	0.2829
		3.625±1.11	3.44±0.885	
	P2	0.4256	0.2192	
	S.calcium	G1	EP	CP
8.22±0.77			7.825±0.975	
G2		CP	EP	0.4707
		8.15±0.885	7.955±0.68	
P2		0.6752	0.6165	
S.Phosphrous		G1	EP	CP
	5.87±1.84		6.14±2.06	
	G2	CP	EP	0.2705
		7.175±3.08	6.545±3.32	
	P2	0.29385	0.7567	
	S.Potassium	G1	EP	CP
5.08±0.67			5.445±0.785	
G2		CP	EP	0.3026
		5.405±0.805	4.95±0.72	
P2		0.36565	0.17155	
S.Sodium		G1	EP	CP
	138.6±2.325		139.55±2.365	
	G2	CP	EP	0.7609
		139.65±4.325	138.55±3.22	
	P2	0.6112	0.5814	
	n1=number of patient in group1 n2= number of patient in group2 G1=Group1 G2=Group2 P1=value for comparing within group P2=value for comparing between group P=independent sample t-test EP=Exercise Phase CP=Control Phase *P<0.05 (significant) HD=Hemodialysis			

TABLE.4 HRQoL & Nutritional parameter within & Between group comparison of both group during Exercise and Control Phase					
Parameter	Group (n1=10) (n2=9)	At Commencement	Phases		P1- value
PCS for HRQoL	G1	33.87 ± 8.92	EP	CP	< 0.0001*
			48.86±6.04	42.835±6.795	
	G2	34.03 ± 7.21	CP	EP	< 0.0001*
			38.475±7.65	50.785±4.235	
	P2	0.9661	0.0433*	0.1382	
	MCS for HRQoL	G1	50.67 ± 4.23	EP	CP
58.395±1.99				52.46±5.175	
G2		52.76 ± 5.82	CP	EP	0.0063*
			54.615	58.615±2.155	
P2		0.3875	0.03125*	0.00535*	
Body Mass Index		G1		EP	CP
	17.555±2.02			15.95±1.98	
	G2		CP	EP	0.7894
			19.3±3.635	19.38±3.365	
	P2		0.2201	0.08275	
	S.Albumin	G1		EP	CP
4.255±0.43				3.995±0.535	
G2			CP	EP	0.4861
			3.99±0.3	4.28±0.395	
P2			0.1842	0.43225	
Total S.Protein		G1		EP	CP
	7.395±0.745			6.96±0.66	
	G2		CP	EP	0.3384
			6.91±0.41	7.3±0.45	
	P2		0.2174	0.42705	
	n1=number of patient in group1, n2= number of patient in group2, G1=Group1, G2=Group2, P1=value for comparing within group, P2=value for comparing between group, P=independent sample t-test, EP=Exercise Phase, CP=Control Phase, *P<0.05 (significant) PCS=Physical Component Summary, MCS=Mental Component Summary, HRQoL= Health Related Quality of Life				

Graph-3 Mean PCS & MCS For HRQoL Group-1

Graph-4 Mean PCS & MCS For HRQoL Group-2

Discussion:

The significant improvement in Kt/V during the exercise phase ($P_2 = 0.0075^*$) aligns with findings by Malini et al. [13], Vogiatzaki et al. [19], and Salhab et al. [20], confirming enhanced dialysis adequacy through intradialytic exercise. However, within-group changes were not statistically significant. Physiological parameters such as blood pressure remained stable ($P_1, P_2 > 0.05$), consistent with studies by Aucella et al. [21] and Mustata et al. [22], indicating the exercise protocol maintains hemodynamic safety without adverse effects. Biochemical comparisons revealed no statistically significant changes (P_1 and $P_2 > 0.05$), yet favorable trends were observed. Hemoglobin increased slightly in Group 2 during exercise, and serum urea, phosphorus, and potassium showed reductions, suggesting improved metabolic handling. These trends support findings by Mohseni et al. [25], Koufaki et al. [23], and Salhab et al. [24], who reported similar non-significant but positive shifts. Creatinine, calcium, and sodium remained stable, echoing the results of Pu et al. [26] and Salhab et al. [24], emphasizing the biochemical safety of intradialytic exercise. Although URR was not statistically analyzed, values derived from pre- and post-dialysis urea levels showed a consistent upward trend during the exercise phases in both groups. This suggests enhanced solute clearance with activity, supporting previous findings by Mohseni et al. (2013) [25] and Chen et al. (2010) [27]. Significant improvements in PCS and MCS scores were observed during the exercise phases in both groups ($P_1 < 0.0001$ and 0.0063), with between-group differences also significant (PCS $P_2 = 0.0433$; MCS $P_2 = 0.03125, 0.00535$), indicating enhanced quality of life due to intradialytic exercise. These results align with studies by Ng et al. [18], El-Said et al. [16], and Cheema et al. [28], which reported improved physical and mental well-being. Although BMI, serum albumin, and total protein showed non-significant positive trends, the direction was consistent with findings by Johansen et al. [29] and Kouidi et al. [30], suggesting potential nutritional benefits. Intradialytic complications were reduced during exercise phases. Episodes of hypotension, cramps, and hypoglycemia were less frequent, with no increase in headaches, hypertension, or gastrointestinal symptoms. These observations confirm the safety and tolerability of intradialytic lower limb exercise among hemodialysis patients.

Conclusion:

This analytical comparative study demonstrates that structured intradialytic lower limb exercise is a safe, feasible, and beneficial addition to routine hemodialysis care. It improved dialysis adequacy (Kt/V), maintained hemodynamic stability, and showed favorable trends in biochemical markers like hemoglobin, urea, phosphorus, and potassium. URR values also trended upward. Quality of life scores improved significantly, and nutritional indicators such as BMI, albumin, and total protein showed positive trends. Intradialytic complications like hypotension and cramps were reduced, with no rise in adverse effects. Overall, this supports integrating structured exercise into routine dialysis sessions to improve patient outcomes in chronic kidney disease.

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